

D5.6 FINAL SUSTAINABILITY STRATEGY

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Abstract	The present document is the final iteration of the sustainability strategy envisaged for RDA in Europe, updating the interim sustainability report released in June 2019.

Dissemination Level

- PU: Public
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Glossary

Abbreviation	Definition
EB	RDA Europe 4.0 Executive Board
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GA	Grant Agreement
GB	RDA Europe 4.0 Governing Board
MS	Member State
NGI	Next Generation Internet
RDA	Research Data Alliance
SG	Secretary General

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Executive Summary

The **European Council Conclusions on Shaping Europe's Digital Future**¹, approved on 9 June 2020, states that “**open science principles and Research Data Alliance recommendations are useful for supporting the decision-making authorities in promoting a flexible common approach for the collection, processing and availability of data**” and welcomes this in the context of the development of EOSC. This is a very significant occurrence and a very important recognition from one of the highest European Union bodies of the value of the work of RDA.

The current RDA Europe 4.0 partners and national nodes, together with the European Commission (INFRAEOSC-03 call) recognise the value of RDA's global forum and European activities and are committed to sustaining them. The strengths of RDA in the European context include the global reach of RDA, its 'neutral' position and platform, its role in forming continental (European) cohesion on matters related to research data, its penetration in national communities through membership at the individual and organisational levels as well via the national nodes, and RDA's role in the broader vision and roadmap for Open Science in Europe, linked to developments within the European Open Science Cloud.

A number of vehicles are possible to operate and finance the future activities of RDA in Europe, and work has been done in the context of the RDA Europe 4.0 project to identify and appraise options, both at the European and national node level. The evaluation and piloting of sustainability paths has required close alignment with developments at the global RDA level, including endorsement of any proposed organisational structure by the RDA Foundation and Council.

Four main RDA Europe sustainability paths from 2021 onwards have been identified:

- A. *The RDA Belgium Foundation*
- B. *The funding streams under the European Framework Programmes (H2020 and Horizon Europe): INFRAEOSC-03 - EOSC Future proposal; EOSC Secretariat open call; FAIRsFAIR*
- C. *The RDA national node network support and the regional engagement programme*
- D. *The in-kind contributions for the continuation of RDA: the RDA Working & Interest Groups*

They will be implemented starting from the official end of the RDA Europe 4.0 project (30 September 2020) to fulfil the following goals:

- *To carry forward the mission of the Research Data Alliance and to consolidate a community organisation of RDA Europe that enables common European contributions to the RDA work and governance, globally.*
- *To support the European community of the Research Data Alliance*
- *To strengthen the role of RDA Europe as a key dedicated interface between the international research data community and the European research data community, specifically the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).*
- *To ensure the daily operations of RDA.*

¹ <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-8711-2020-INIT/en/pdf>

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the document

The main goal of the present document, jointly developed with contributions from all RDA Europe 4.0 Consortium Partners and national nodes, is to define the sustainability path for RDA in Europe after the end of the RDA Europe 4.0 project (30 September 2020). The sustainability path included in this report has been endorsed by the governing bodies of RDA in Europe, namely the Executive Board (EB) and the RDA Europe Governing Board (GB) and by the RDA Council.

1.2 Background work and related deliverables

The present document has been jointly developed by the Consortium Partners with the support of the RDA Europe 4.0 national nodes, building on what was originally written in the GA /1/ and leveraging on the previous work on RDA Europe sustainability conducted in the context of RDA Europe 3 aligning focus with the key developments in the European and global research data, infrastructures and Open Science landscape.

A first interim release of this document has been submitted to the European Commission in the context of the RDA Europe 4.0 project in July 2019.

2 Goals and principal components of the sustainability strategy for RDA in Europe

The **goals** of the sustainability strategy for RDA in Europe described in this document can be summarised as follows:

1. *To carry forward the mission of the Research Data Alliance and to consolidate a community organisation of RDA Europe that enables common European contributions to the RDA work and governance, globally.*
2. *To support the European community of the Research Data Alliance*
3. *To strengthen the role of RDA Europe as a key dedicated interface between the international research data community and the European research data community, specifically the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).*
4. *To ensure the daily operations of RDA.*

Each of the goals requires specific measures both financially and organisationally and an approach of co-creation and coordination between RDA Europe, RDA global and European developments (especially EOSC).

Principal components of the sustainability strategy of RDA Europe can be described along the 4 goals, introduced above:

1. To carry forward the mission of the Research Data Alliance and to consolidate a community organisation of RDA Europe that enables common European contributions to the RDA work and governance, globally.

RDA is a cooperative international organisation that “builds the social and technical bridges to enable the open sharing and re-use of data”.² As such, it is dedicated to serve the global community for the benefit of society at large: RDA’s vision is researchers and innovators openly sharing data across technologies, disciplines and geographies to address the grand challenges of society. Participants’ contributions to RDA and benefits from RDA are in a dynamic equilibrium to be managed in joint responsibility of all participants. Europe has been one of the regions that have been committed to

² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/about-rda>

supporting the global operations as well as the pan-regional community-building programmes since 2012. Individuals contributing to RDA are usually employed at an institution in a given country that jointly form the European Research Area. RDA Europe 4.0 has supported the building of national nodes in order to increase the impact of RDA at national levels, increase community engagement in a scalable manner and support alignment between countries. While the internal organisation and sustainability of each national node is not a primary subject of RDA Europe, an inclusive and participatory organisation of a community organisation of RDA Europe constitutes a genuine European dimension.

For the sustainability strategy of RDA Europe, the commitment of RDA Europe to the mission of the Research Data Alliance will continue under the coordination of the established RDA Europe legal entity with the support and engagement of the network of national nodes established during the RDA Europe 4.0 project and via the global regional engagement programme.

2. To support the European community of the Research Data Alliance.

Work in RDA is predominantly undertaken by individuals, active in interest groups, working groups, organisation and governance. For example, technicians contribute specifications originating from projects and services in their original environment and benefit from broader expertise, standardisation and adoption internationally. Data professionals harmonize their workflows and policies to make data widely and mutually accessible.

European individuals form a specific community in that many projects and services have a European dimension and are organized at a European level to ensure (a) an adequate representation of European individuals in RDA and (b) to support the development of a diverse and strong European RDA community with respect to representation of research subjects, gender, age, cultures and regions. Participation of the European community is based on in-kind contributions complemented by some activities supported by RDA Europe 4.0 through specific funding instruments, implemented mainly as cascading grants.

For the sustainability strategy of RDA Europe, the specific support measures for the European volunteer community will continue through EC project funding (namely the awarded project under the INFRAEOSC-03 call³).

3. To strengthen the role of RDA Europe as one dedicated interface between the international research data community and the European research data community, specifically the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Together, the individual and common European dimension of participation in RDA form a bidirectional interface between the international research data community and the European research data community. EOSC is currently being built to align contributions of individuals, countries and Europe and therefore optimally positioned to help define the exact implementation for RDA Europe to act as such an interface. While RDA Europe must maintain neutrality towards RDA globally, and can thus not be subsumed under EOSC, RDA Europe can serve as a facilitator for both processing inputs from Europe through EOSC to RDA globally and processing outputs from RDA globally to Europe through EOSC.

For the sustainability strategy of RDA Europe, RDA Europe will act as the bridge between the EOSC and the international data research community through EC project funding, namely the

³ <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/infraeosc-03-2020-integration-and-consolidation-existing-pan-european-access-mechanism-public>

INFRAEOSC03 call and the further evolution of the RDA Global Open Research Commons Interest Group.

4. To ensure the daily operations ('business') of RDA.

Participations in work and governance of RDA are one type of activity, daily business operations are another type activity. Both types are strictly interdependent because business operations guarantee the social and technical platform (e.g. plenaries and website) of RDA to contribute to and receive benefits from RDA and contributions are necessary for the platform to function.

The business operations follow a co-funding model between states and regions (e.g. Europe, US, Australia) and are organised in the RDA Secretariat. The RDA Europe 4.0 project will provide the European contribution to RDA until 30 September 2020.

For the sustainability strategy of RDA Europe, RDA Europe will contribute to the funding of the RDA Secretariat activities with resources coming in via the RDA Europe legal entity and via the global regional engagement programme.

In order to meet the sustainability objectives described above, there are several core activities of RDA Europe which need to be sustained. These comprise supporting the European RDA community and data professionals to adopt the mission of RDA via a range of outreach activities and cascading grants.

The table below summarizes the RDA Europe 4.0 motivational mechanisms and the sustainability schemes identified in the RDA Europe 4.0 project to support the engagement of the RDA community in Europe after the end of the project.

Motivational mechanism	Description of main benefits	Revenue stream for RDA in Europe
Mechanism 1 – Visibility & reputation	As per the core mission of RDA.	RDA BE Foundation + Regional Engagement programme
Mechanism 2 – Incentive/Financial-driven	The cascading grant mechanism, as successfully experienced also during RDA Europe 4.0, constitutes a fundamental lever to incentivise rapid participation of individuals and organisations (including SMEs) in RDA.	Financial support to third parties through the INFRAEOSC-03 call wishing to engage in the RDA processes for the RDA outputs adoption fostering interoperability and service composition in the EOSC portal. Insertion of RDA Europe in cascading grants schemes to further distribute targeted grants to its community to perform various R&I tasks.
Mechanism 3– Knowledge-driven (synergies with other strategic goals part of the EC Work Programmes)	RDA Europe 4.0 is contributing to further establishing the role of RDA as the reference, authoritative, global information source for Europe's effort in research data policies themes and future developments and as the bridge between the European Open Science	The financial support to 3rd parties through the INFRAEOSC-03 call, especially researchers wishing to engage in the RDA processes for the RDA outputs adoption fostering interoperability and service composition in the EOSC Portal could be granted for work on specific challenges that contribute to the service and data offering on the EOSC portal.

	Cloud (EOSC) and the international community.	The further evolution of the RDA Global Open Research Commons Interest Group as the instrument bridging the EOSC with the international community and supporting what is called the Work of RDA (see more details in Section 3).
Mechanism 4 – Event-driven	Support the continued participation to plenaries.	The financial support of the Plenary co-hosts , of the plenary fees complemented with additional support by the INFRAEOSC-03 call
Mechanism 5 – Technical Specifications-driven	Activities linked and/or generated by development of technical specifications will be utilised as the opportunity to interest & eventually on-board early users, and community members in general, across Europe.	There are currently eight RDA recommendations and ICT technical specifications that have been approved and four are currently in the process of evaluation. The ICT technical specifications process in Europe will be supported by the INFRAEOSC-03 call and will become the reference process for the EOSC technical specifications

Table 1: Motivational mechanisms supporting engagement and impact on prospect revenues

3 Components of the global Business and Work of RDA to be sustained

In order to discuss, define and develop a sustainability model for the RDA in Europe, a series of different elements and considerations must be made. The table below outlines some of the elements required to assess different solutions to sustain, maintain and grow the RDA community in Europe.

One distinction between the two major components of RDA is important to explain sustainability requirements:

- ✓ The **Business** of RDA is to support the global community and facilitate the building and using of bridges that enable open sharing and reuse of data.
- ✓ The **Work** of RDA is done by the volunteer community through self-formed, focused Working Groups and exploratory Interest Groups to build the social and technical connections or bridges.

The tables below outline the estimated costs and components required to support, respectively, the global Business and the Work of RDA on an annual basis. These costs are based on the current programmes and activities supported centrally and/or regionally. With regards to the estimates of the budget dedicated to travels, it refers to the pre-COVID situation therefore these costs might be lower in the future. A revised travel budget will be calculated in 2022, analysing the trends of the costs between 2020 and 2022.

Strategic element	Description	Estimated Cost
In-kind & Staff	Secretariat tasks (communications, event management, group and community support, governance body support, to support the plenaries, the WG & IGs, etc.). Both Direct and In-kind of support are required: In-kind: at least 0.5 FTE contributed by each contributing region ⁴ (may increase depending on the size of region) to support RDA secretariat costs	In-kind

⁴ An RDA Region is loosely defined as a “national level” geographic entity or consortium of “national-level” entities, and is intended to be broadly representative. A “contributing region” is an RDA region that has signed a partnership agreement with RDA Foundation (UK)

Directly Employed Staff	Contribution to the annual cost of Direct employees: at least 3 FTEs	200k€/year
Technical Directors	Staff costs to cover the technical direction and support for RDA recommendation implementation and maintenance	250k€/year
Staff Travel	Cost related to staff travel (not including Secretary General) based on past years and staff estimates. A revised calculation may be made at the end of 2021 when new travel patterns (post COVID19) are clearer.	250k€/year
Governance Body Support	Costs of travel and subsistence for Council, TAB & OAB members	200k€/year
Secretary General	Costs (salary, overhead & travel) of Secretary General	250k€/year
Web Platform	Development and maintenance of the RDA web platform	100k€/year
RDA Foundation Admin & Legal	Operating costs (admin, accounting, legal, hosting of the website, domain services, other)	100k€/year
Communication and Branding	RDA material and other branding costs	150k€/year
Consultancy	Costs related to ad-hoc reports, studies, impact assessment	100k€/year
Events	RDA workshops, training, event costs (not including RDA plenary meetings)	50k€/year
Miscellaneous	Miscellaneous costs	50k€/year
	<i>Subtotal of the costs above</i>	<i>1,700 k€/year</i>

Table 2: Main elements constituting the costs of supporting the Business of RDA

In Table 2, the (ideal⁵) costs of the Work are indicated.

Strategic element	Description	Estimated Cost	Notes
Early Career	Support for the participation of early career researchers in RDA plenary meetings	250k€/year	through cascading grants
Experts	Support for technical implementation, maintenance, quality control, and adoption of RDA outputs and recommendations	150k€/year	case to case basis according to output / recommendation
Adoption Grants	Financial contribution of 20k€ per grant for short adoption and implementation projects	300k€/year	cascading grants
RDA Group Chairs	Costs of travel and subsistence for RDA group chairs	200k€/year	case by case basis
Regional Leadership meetings	Support for travel and logistics of regional workshops	150k€/year	participants only
Awards	Bi-annual awards and fellow support for Early career and special contributions and achievements by community members (10K€ each)	250k€/year	open application

⁵ In fact, this is what could ideally be supported. However, grants could be scaled back, prioritising support to attend plenaries / engage in RDA.

Grant Evaluations	Costs to cover evaluators, reviewers, of cascading grants	150k€/year	evaluators directly
Ad hoc group / community support	Miscellaneous costs related to RDA group members	150k€/year	
<i>Subtotal of the costs above</i> □			1,600 k€/year

Table 3: Main elements constituting the costs of supporting the Work of RDA

The total costs of RDA Business plus RDA Work would therefore amount to 3.3 M€ annually.

4 Strategic foundations: RDA global strategy

On a global level, the RDA governance bodies (Council, Technical Advisory Board, Organisational Advisory Board and Secretariat) define the global vision and strategy for the Alliance. In 2020, a new board has been created, the Regional Advisory Board, aimed at bringing the regional perspectives into the RDA governance.

Figure 1: The RDA governance 2020

4.1 The RDA value proposition and its assets vs the challenge of “sustainability”

As indicated in D5.1 “Communication, Marketing & Stakeholders Engagement Plan”, a number of elements of the RDA value proposition can effectively contribute to the envisaged sustainability path. These elements are schematically indicated in the table below.

Asset	Value for revenue generation	Potential source of revenues
Forum	The core value of RDA lies in the forum it provides. This increases efficiency for members delivering new outputs as they can reach global consensus and create more resilient solutions. Moreover, it provides a space for commercial providers to connect with potential user communities, and a vehicle for research funders to engage with one another and the broader stakeholder community.	Fees for attending plenaries; Income from project proposals; Fees from participating organisations (e.g. OAB)
Outputs	The RDA outputs are an incredibly valuable asset.	Fees for service (if a

	Although openly-licensed, services could be generated on these as a source of revenue. RDA could become a network through which services are provided.	business model supporting it can be designed in the future)
Knowledge	The RDA community is a rich source of knowledge on research data issues. RDA could act as a broker to connect people requiring project partners, services and consultancy.	Match-making fees. Income from project proposals.

Table 4: RDA assets vs potential for revenue generation

4.2 Global revenue streams

Currently, the revenue streams supporting the global operations are indicated in the table below.

Revenue stream	Type of funding	In-kind contribution (Staff)
1. International grant funding (EC, NSF, etc)	Annual fixed contribution	Yes
2. Direct Project / grant participation	Project based, time limited project financing	No
3. Funding agency contribution	Fixed contribution, time limited	No
4. Regional Engagement⁶	Annual financial contribution	Yes
5. Organisational membership fees	Annual fee	No
6. RDA Plenary Registration Fees	5% Net Plenary fee revenue (since 2019)	No

Table 5: Revenue streams at global level

Three regions have been supporting both the global operations (via the RDA Foundation) and pan-regional community building programmes since 2012, namely: Australia, Europe and the United States.

The size and scope of the regional programme varies in each of the regions but all financially contribute to the global operational costs through a direct annual financial contribution to the RDA Foundation and in-kind staff resources for the RDA Secretariat.

4.3 The RDA Regional Engagement Programme

As the RDA community rapidly grows (from 8 to almost 11,000 individuals from academia, industry, and government, representing over 145 countries in numerous disciplines, in just over 7 years), RDA recognises that strong partnerships with its Regional members are crucial to its success as an international organisation. With this goal in mind, a global Regional Engagement Task Force examined and outlined the complementary and mutually-beneficial relationship between RDA and its Regions.

4.3.1 Background

The Regional Engagement meeting at P11 (March 2018) was the start of a much larger conversation. There are numerous complexities in Regional Engagement. This meeting was a first step towards formalising an organisational approach. The meeting began with an overview of Regional perspectives through short presentations from each attending representative from Australia, Austria, Europe, Germany, Iberia (including Spain and Portugal), Japan, North America (including Canada and the United States), and the United Kingdom. RDA then presented their priorities. The discussion articulated important topics from the presentations and the white paper offered by Council's Regional Engagement Subcommittee. These topics were prioritized through a voting exercise, and a small Regional

⁶ Based on the financial contributions and terms outlined in the RDA Global Regional Engagement Framework - <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-regions>

Engagement Task Force of Regional representatives was formed. Regional Representatives and Council members met weekly from March to June 2018 to create an initial draft document outlining the relationships between RDA and the Regions, and a framework for the expectations and management of Regional partners. The draft framework was reviewed by Council at their June 2018 meeting and adjusted in light of their feedback. A session took place at the RDA 12th Plenary, 6 November 2018 in Gaborone to share the proposal with the community at large and agree on a final framework to put forward for implementation. Following feedback from different regional representatives from across the globe, the Regional Engagement Task Force reconvened in April 2019 to begin the definition of the governance model of Regional Engagement and to work on test cases of individual RDA Foundation - regional memorandum of understanding or Partnership Agreements. This framework is the basis for enlarging the RDA regional connections.

4.3.2 Purpose and goals

The Research Data Alliance needs to act on multiple levels. As a global organisation, it provides a powerful, international forum to reach consensus on data standards and interoperability frameworks. However, the adoption of standards and practices happens at a local level, so a combination of global and regional activities are required to assist in the implementation of outputs. Regions also play a key role in representing the practices and interests of their communities within the RDA and placing these on a global stage. The Research Data Alliance and Regions have a symbiotic, mutually-beneficial relationship.

The RDA recognises that each Region will be unique with different values, goals, governance, funding sources, etc. The purpose of the Regional Engagement Programme is to provide a general framework for the creation and management of RDA Regions that will benefit both parties while maintaining alignment and coordination. The goals are to:

- Establish a network of Regions which can play a dual role in representing regional interests in the global RDA forum, and disseminating outputs for local adoption
- Propose a common framework of mutually-beneficial activities that can be adapted in formal arrangements with the RDA Foundation to meet the context of each Region
- Define appropriate, scaled levels of contribution (financial, in-kind and other) that enable the development of Regions in all areas of the globe and do not advantage or disadvantage certain groups
- Develop governance structures to enable Regions to have a voice in shaping the future directions and priorities of the RDA

4.3.3 Current status and next steps

Regional engagement is still one of the highest priorities for RDA and is central in the RDA Strategic Plan (2020-2023). In 2019, RDA global signed a regional partnership with the French Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation (MESRI – Ministère de l'Enseignement Supérieur, de la Recherche et de l'Innovation) and the French Centre national de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS). Support for RDA France⁷ is part of the French National Strategy for Open Science (Plan National pour la Science Ouverte PNSO⁸), launched by MESRI in July 2018.

RDA Global signed a partnership agreement with the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) in May 2020, for a three year financial and in-kind contribution to support the Work of RDA.

Further partnership agreements, at different stages of negotiation, are currently under discussion with Canada, Finland, and the United States of America.

5 RDA Europe legacy and sustainability

The RDA Europe 4.0 project has been a key contributor to the future sustainability of RDA. The

⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-france>

⁸ <https://www.ouvrirelascience.fr/national-plan-for-open-science-4th-july-2018/>

paragraphs below show how the RDA Europe 4.0 project has supported RDA between 2018-2020, the additional funds received in the same period and how RDA Europe will be supported from 2021 on.

5.1 RDA Europe 4.0 support between 2018-2020

The RDA Europe 4.0 project has supported the mission and operation of RDA global, the engagement of the European community and the positioning of RDA in the EOSC landscape for the full duration of the project from March 2018 until September 2020.

This section describes the main assets developed and maintained by the RDA Europe 4.0 project to deliver its achievements.

5.1.1 Support to the RDA business between 2018-2020

RDA global web platform development & maintenance

The RDA Global Platform is an essential component of the day-to-day operations of RDA Global. It is a working platform that supports collaboration, communication, consensus and knowledge exchange. Built by the RDA Europe partner Trust-IT, using the Drupal Open Source platform, it provides dedicated working areas for the RDA Working, Interest Groups, and coordination bodies. It is the main communication and dissemination channel for all RDA activities.

The RDA Europe 4.0 supported the further development and maintenance of the platform between 2018-2020.

Main technical enhancements done during the project:

- Better mapping of RDA assets with the creation of a Dynamic RDA Recommendation & Outputs Catalogue⁹ and the integration of the RDA Atlas of Knowledge to support better outputs visualization
- Enhancement of the time of response of the RDA website
- Automatization of the plenary management process (session publication, posters publication, etc.)
- Implementation of the Case statement Request for Comments¹⁰
- Improved internal website search¹¹
- Organisational members dynamic map
- RDA internal roles management (new functionalities to enable content management and visualisation based on the RDA roles - chairs, co-chairs, members, TAB, etc.)
- Improved user experience and graphical layout of the Group pages¹²
- An online catalogue of all RDA-related publications via the OpenAIRE dashboard
- Improvement of user activity analytics¹³
- New privacy policy aligned with GDPR

⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/catalogue>

¹⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/request-for-comments>

¹¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/search/site/>

¹² In order to make it easier for users to collaborate with their teams, at the beginning of 2020 the user experience of RDA Groups' online space was improved. A series of icons and labels now guide users' activity and help them post messages to the group members, create and organise wiki pages, send event announcements, publish and organise the outputs and case statements resulting from the group's activity, and browse all the members of each Group. A dedicated announcement was included in the February 2020 RDA global newsletter <https://www.rd-alliance.org/february-newsletter-p15-highlights-reports-and-news-adoption-stories-and-more>

¹³ Different views allow specific type of users to retrieve structure data, like overall details of the groups (<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groupdetails> - available for Secretariat and TAB), group membership/country (<https://www.rd-alliance.org/statistics/users/users-groups> - available for Node Coordinators)

The full description of the implementations carried out is captured in the RDA website roadmap¹⁴.

In addition to the new implementations, RDA Europe, via its partner TRUST-IT, took care of the hosting and maintenance of the website: a dedicated technical team has also been appointed to address all the technical issues emerged during the project and address the technical requests coming from the community.

Support to the RDA Secretariat

The Secretariat supports the administrative, logistical, and other activities of the RDA. The RDA secretariat is internationally distributed and the RDA Europe 4.0 project has supported it with contributions of 6 European members in the following roles:

- Web manager: Coordination Implementation Web Roadmap, Web content coordination, Global Communication task force, Plenary support, Maintenance RDA web environment, RDA in a nutshell production
- Outreach & Impact Coordinator and Support: Adoption task force coordination, Outputs and Recommendation facilitation, TAB liaison
- Document management support : RDA repository and contents management
- Plenary Support: Coordination, organisation and promotion of RDA plenaries;
- Affiliate and Organisational Member liaison: Support OAB procedures, actions and website; Tracks and processes memberships, including invoicing and tax issues; member recruitment and negotiation of MoUs
- RDA Foundation administrative support: Support to the administration of the RDA UK Foundation.

Support to the RDA Governance

TAB support: The Technical Advisory Board (TAB) is responsible for the technical direction of RDA and provides technical expertise and advice to RDA Council, as well as helping to develop and review RDA Working and Interest Groups to promote their impact and effectiveness. One of the members of the RDA EU 4.0 project has been assigned the task to liaise with TAB. The TAB liaisons ensure TAB has access to all up-to-date information, technical infrastructure and operational support needed to focus on its core activities. All support is aligned, monitored, documented and updated through the weekly secretariat meetings, bi-weekly TAB meetings and TAB documents and wiki spaces.

OAB support: The Organisational Advisory Board (OAB) is composed of representatives of the Organisational Members also known as the Organisational Assembly. One RDA EU Secretariat member has been assigned the task to liaise with OAB. The TAB liaisons ensure TAB has access to all up-to-date information, technical infrastructure and operational support needed to focus on its core activities. All support is aligned, monitored, documented and updated through the weekly secretariat meetings, monthly OAB meetings and OAB documents and wiki spaces.

Secretary General Salary: RDA Europe 4.0 has provided financial support to RDA covering part of the costs of the salary of the Secretary General.

Travel financial support to the EU members of the RDA governance: To ensure the active European participation to the RDA Governing bodies (Council, OAB, TAB, Secretariat) while adopting an inclusive approach and making sure that experts with the right profile and background are engaged and are supported in taking up leading roles in RDA, the RDA Europe project provided financial and administrative support for EU members of the RDA governing bodies.

5.1.2 Support to the RDA work

Engagement of the RDA Europe community

The RDA individual membership increased from 3,398 European community members (March 2018) to over 5,700 members (5,726 July 2020).

¹⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/sites/default/files/RDA%20website%20revised%20Roadmap.pdf>

The cascading grants mechanism

A series of open calls targeting Early Careers, Experts, Ambassadors, Adoption projects and National Nodes, implemented using the cascading grant schemes (Annex K of Grant Agreement) have consolidated and increased the European contribution to RDA as well as the take-up and implementation of RDA results across all scientific domains and European organisations.

RDA Europe 4.0 took care of the design, publication and promotion of all the different calls (all consortium partners), the management of the contracts of the awarded grantees (UGOE) and the set up of an online grants management platform (TRUST-IT) and of a recruitment mechanism for external evaluators (TRUST-IT) to ensure a transparent selection process.

The grants management platform has been brought to the RDA Europe 4.0 project by Trust-IT as background knowledge. The RDA EU 4.0 instantiation has been customised as part of the project, so all partners (and in particular the RDAF) will be ensured in the future to have royalty-free access to it. The current version of the grants platform (to be specific, the one operational on NGLatlantic.eu), is the TRUST-GRANTS™¹⁵ product, trademarked by Trust-IT. TRUST-GRANTS, if it is adopted by any future funded project, will enter that project as background knowledge of Trust-IT under the following conditions:

- A. SaaS licensing of 10k€/y;
- B. Customisation effort to deliver the specific instantiation, depending on the requirements given;
- C. Weekly maintenance/evolution & technical assistance.

Specific calls to select external evaluators appointed for the grants selection process have been delivered. At the end of the project 20 external experts have acted as evaluators. This pool of evaluators can be used in any future RDA cascading grants processes.

The RDA Plenary Meetings and the European Events

RDA Europe 4.0 has contributed significant effort to the organisation and management of RDA plenaries¹⁶ (P11, P12/IDW, P13, P14, P15, P16) and has financially supported the organisation of the two European Plenaries held during the project (P11 Berlin, P14 Helsinki). RDA EU has contributed to activities throughout the lifecycle of the events from scoping to composing and distributing call for contributions, coordinating submissions, engaging with those accepted directly and through mass communications and creating online resources, and assisting with testing and management of GTM accounts to enable remote participation to RDA plenaries. RDA Europe 4.0 has also provided marketing, branding and graphic design support. RDA Europe 4.0 has also supported the organisation of other RDA European events such as the EOSC event organised in colocation with the RDA Plenary 14 in Helsinki.

The ambassadors programme

The [RDA Europe Ambassadors](https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-disciplines/rda-europe-ambassadors)¹⁷ are a group of experts that are working on better connecting the RDA

¹⁵ <https://www.trust-it-services.com/products/trust-grants>

¹⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries>

¹⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-disciplines/rda-europe-ambassadors>

with the domain focused communities. Set up as a grants stream under the RDA Europe 4.0 project, the Ambassadors programme has facilitated an alternative way of engaging with the RDA that follows the discipline/domain specific paths. The RDA Europe 4.0 cohort is made up of 14 Ambassadors that cover broader domains such as Natural Sciences, Social Sciences and Humanities, Agricultural Sciences and more focused topics such as the Sustainable Development Goals and approaches such as Interdisciplinary Research. To support and widen this two-way communication channel, the Ambassadors have produced a set of key resources and set up activities to be taken forward beyond the project lifetime including discipline pages (e.g. [RDA and Scholarly Communication](#)) and reports highlighting the value of RDA for specific domain (e.g. [RDA for the Social Sciences](#), [RDA for the Humanities](#)). The Ambassadors have set up or driven domain/topic focused groups (e.g. [Interest group on RDA for the Sustainable Development Goals](#)) and developed training resources (e.g. [Bioinformatics](#)).

The national node network

The RDA Europe 4.0 project has built a capillary network of 22 national nodes¹⁸ that are proactively working to provide input and content to enrich the National Digital Agendas of the EU countries and supporting the promotion and adoption of RDA Outputs and recommendations in their countries and in the European Open Science Cloud.

Contributions to the RDA Outputs & Adoption Process

RDA Outputs have been adopted by over 50 European organisations, as indicated in the list of RDA adoption use-cases¹⁹. The RDA Europe 4.0 project has supported the publication and promotion of the outputs and the documentation of related adoption stories. In particular, the RDA Europe 4.0 project has worked on inspiring further uptake of RDA outputs by sharing challenges, best practices and lessons learned in the shape of adoption stories, published on the RDA website by funding 6 adoption projects²⁰ and stimulating the submission of papers for the RDA special collection on the *CODATA Data Science Journal*²¹.

ICT Technical Specifications

RDA is not a standards development organisation (SDO), but has been building synergies with the Multi-Stakeholders Platform on ICT Standardisation (MSP - E02758) becoming an organisation authorised to submit recommendations that can get a fast track to becoming standards. Eight RDA Recommendations were submitted before the start of the RDA Europe 4.0 project (4 of which were approved as technical specifications). During the project a third wave of 4 extra recommendations have been submitted to the MPS and a fourth submission is under preparation²².

Support to the GEDE group

The RDA Europe 4.0 has financially supported the work of the RDA GEDE Group²³ to maintain and expand the network of GEDE experts (to now including over 150 experts from more than 50 infrastructure initiatives in Europe) and support their work in the realm of PIDs and Digital Objects such as Data Fabric, Data Foundation & Terminology, Dynamic Data Citation, Kernel Information, Data Collections, Data Type Registries, PID Information Types, and others.

RDA & EOSC

RDA Europe 4.0 has strengthened RDA's contribution to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

During the project, a series of collaborations have been established with a set of EOSC-related projects: EOSC-hub, OpenAIRE, FREYA, FAIRsFAIR, EOSC Secretariat, etc. all documented in the deliverable D3.3²⁴. A series of workshops has been run to discuss services to make data FAIR offered by the

¹⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-europe>

¹⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/adoption-stories>; <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/adoption-recommendations>

²⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/rda-europe-adoption-grants>

²¹ <https://datascience.codata.org/collections/special/research-data-alliance-results/>

²² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/standards>

²³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/gede-group-european-data-experts-rda>

²⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3630264>

different initiatives and related gaps²⁵.

To further consolidate the role of RDA as the place where to meet the international research data community, the EOSC Executive Board has reached out to the RDA Europe 4.0 project to organise an EOSC workshop in conjunction with the Helsinki Plenary 14 of RDA²⁶. With 230 participants active in Open Science from 33 different countries, the event offered an open platform for policy makers and representatives from academia and research to discuss open science and data commons initiatives from Africa, Australia, Canada, Europe and Japan. The event gave insights into global trends and how the European Open Science Cloud is positioned itself in this global setting, and importantly, highlighted what the necessary steps are for its effective and quick establishment. The event also confirmed EOSC as a vehicle for quality science to maximise socio-economic impact.

In 2019, RDA has publicly announced on the rd-alliance.org portal its value proposition for the EOSC²⁷. RDA is officially represented in the EOSC current governance by Juan Bicarregui, member of the EOSC Executive Board and chair of the EOSC Sustainability Working Group. Many RDA Working and Interest Groups chairs are actively involved in the EOSC FAIR Working Group.

5.2 RDA Europe additional support 2018-2020

During the RDA Europe 4.0 project, extra funding has been brought to the European component of RDA via an H2020 EC funded project: FAIRsFAIR. The details of the support gained through this project are reported in the following paragraph as the activities performed in these projects will continue also after 2020.

5.3 RDA Europe support 2021 onwards

In April 2020, the RDA Global under the guidance and custodianship of the RDA global Council, established a Belgian based legal entity. This non-profit organisation, entitled RDA Foundation BE (RDAF BE) is an ASBL (*association sans but lucratif*) which will be transformed into an AISBL (*association internationale sans but lucratif*) in the second half of 2020. RDAF BE has the same mission, vision and values as RDA global, but focuses on representing, supporting, and growing the RDA community in Europe. To all intent and purposes, it is the legal representation of the European RDA community.

The organisation actively seeks appropriate funding and partnerships to support the European RDA community, through grants, agreements and collaborations that ensure the engagement of all European stakeholders. Furthermore, the RDAF BE will contribute directly to RDA Global through financial and in-kind support, via a regional engagement partnership agreement.

At the time of writing this deliverable (July 2020), the RDAF BE trustees and RDA Council are defining the strategic plan for RDAF BE 2020 - 2023, in line with the global strategic plan, which will include the mechanisms and processes to enlarge the European membership and ensure open and inclusive engagement with relevant European stakeholders.

5.3.1 The funding streams under the European Framework Programmes (H2020 and Horizon Europe)

RDA being part of the current and upcoming work programmes is a clear opportunity that will be pursued, also as far as the sustainability of the RDA in Europe is concerned. RDA, as an open, international forum, is seen in the European landscape, as key in facilitating the European contribution to the development of global data infrastructures needs and the RDA Europe series of funding projects, with European consortia, in the past five years have primarily been to ensure Europe's role as a global player. The objectives of the RDA Europe funded projects have been achieved by strengthening and consolidating Europe's contribution to the Research Data Alliance (RDA), ensuring that RDA fosters

²⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2020.100058>

²⁶ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/international-research-data-community-contributing-eosc>

²⁷ <https://rd-alliance.org/value-research-data-alliance-european-open-science-cloud-eosc>

research data interoperability and exchange at global level.

RDA is seen today as a fitting global forum to engage scientific communities in defining best practices for data exchange and interoperability, especially for those who have underdeveloped data infrastructures. In the context of EOSC and its needs, Europe is known to be the largest producer of publicly-funded research data but this data is not exploited well enough. Therefore, RDA can be seen as the forum where international minds look at data management, infrastructure on campus/university levels, national, regional, European and global levels too. It also places Europe in a leading position in enabling the use of the world's store of research data in multi-disciplinary, data-intensive global scientific collaborations.

Specific recognition of the RDA contribution in Europe and globally, include:

The **European Open Science Policy Platform (OSPP)**, of which RDA has been an active, invited member since its inception in 2014, published their final report²⁸ in May 2020. On page 12, in reference to the conclusion to set up a “OSPP registry of pilots and implementations of responsible metrics” note **“To this end, we are working towards the development of a structured registry (similar in nature to clinicaltrials.gov to ensure full searchability), initiated and shaped by the OSPP and coordinated by the Research Data Alliance (RDA)”**. RDAF BE is currently actively seeking funding to begin this work, which will have a global perspective.

The **European Council Conclusions on Shaping Europe's Digital Future**²⁹, approved on 9 June 2020, states that **“open science principles and Research Data Alliance recommendations are useful for supporting the decision-making authorities in promoting a flexible common approach for the collection, processing and availability of data”** and welcomes this in the context of the development of EOSC. This is a very significant occurrence and a very important recognition from one of the highest European Union bodies of the work of RDA.

Finally, in preparation for the new European Union funding framework, a Proposal for a European partnership under European Commission's Horizon Europe funding programme focusing on **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership**³⁰ was launched at the end of May and states **“The Research Data Alliance (RDA) has become a recognised actor in the development of standards and good practices for managing research data. [...] Many EOSC-projects have already taken concrete initiatives to partner with these organisations and to participate in RDA Working Groups. These relationships will be extended as EOSC reaches new milestones.”** A further recognition of the importance of the global RDA community contribution to the European research and open science arena.

The recent (28 May 2020) **G7 Science and Technology Ministers' Declaration on COVID-19: A Shared Vision for Science and Technology in Responding to the Pandemic, Protecting Human Health, and Promoting Social and Economic Recovery**³¹ recognized the impact that the COVID-19 pandemic has had on people's health, well-being, and livelihoods. The G7 Leaders' Statement on COVID-19 expressed the need for a strongly coordinated international approach, based on science and evidence, consistent with democratic values, including encouraging science, research, and technology cooperation and utilizing the strengths of private enterprise. Specifically, the statement focused on the aspects that RDA has been addressing through the COVID-19 Recommendations and Guidelines on data sharing³². Namely, make government-sponsored COVID-19 epidemiological and related research results, data, and information accessible to the public in machine-readable formats, to the greatest extent possible, in accordance with relevant laws and regulations, including privacy and intellectual property laws. Identify research results, data, and information crucial to addressing the current COVID-

²⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm?pg=open-science-policy-platform>

²⁹ <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-8711-2020-INIT/en/pdf>

³⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/research_and_innovation/funding/documents/ec_rtd_he-partnership-open-science-cloud-eosc.pdf

³¹ <https://www.state.gov/g7-science-and-technology-ministers-declaration-on-covid-19/>

³² **RDA COVID-19 Working Group. Recommendations and Guidelines on data sharing. Research Data Alliance, 2020.** DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00052>

19 pandemic response and to preventing potential future pandemics, in an effort to advance research, clinical care, public health, and public communication. Identify current data gaps, make anonymized data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, and recognize the importance of open science, which increases public accessibility to research results and data. Exchange best practices and lessons learned on the ethical and transparent use of data in the COVID-19 response and beyond. Share tools and methods for responsible use of data, and for more transparent, participatory, and accountable use of data, recognizing ongoing initiatives, including on repositories.

Past funding opportunities from the European union funded programmes under FP7 and Horizon2020 for RDA in Europe meant calls focusing on RDA called for:

- establishing coordination mechanisms at European level (national research funders, European education and research associations) and with international organisations dealing with standardisation, research data and education issues (IETF, W3C, CODATA, OECD, UNESCO, etc.);
- engaging research communities at early stages of standards development and addressing common data requirements for new services, bringing together users and technology providers;
- promoting sustainable models for research data sharing and installing trust in the adopted solutions;
- helping the development and adoption of relevant international open standards based on the best practices of a large spectrum of research communities.

Much of the future EC funding prioritises **RDA playing a role to the EOSC initiative and in particular to the context of the EOSC portal**. In fact, the contribution of RDA to the EOSC initiative & in particular to the context of the EOSC portal proposals could also provide financial support to 3rd parties wishing to engage and participate in RDA processes and activities, including RDA outputs adoption fostering interoperability and service composition in the EOSC portal.

5.3.1.1 INFRAEOSC-03 - EOSC Future proposal

In June 2020, a proposal entitled “EOSC Future” was submitted under the EC call INFRAEOSC-03. Support for RDA was specifically cited in the call text “*ii. Support to the Research Data Alliance’s contribution to the EOSC:*”

- *Proposals retained for funding should directly support the contribution of RDA to the EOSC initiative and, in particular, in the context of the EOSC Portal.*
- *Proposals should also provide financial support to third parties wishing to engage and participate in the Research Data Alliance processes and activities, including RDA outputs adoption fostering the interoperability and service composition in the EOSC Portal.”*

RDAF BE is a member of the large consortium that submitted the proposal, and if successful, the project and related activities, responding directly to the call requirements, will start in January 2021.

5.3.1.2 EOSC Secretariat open call

RDAF BE will respond to an open call, due to be published by the EOSC Secretariat in July 2020, to support the creation of open global data sharing and reuse standards and solutions to support the implementation of the EOSC. This will also include the creation of a global rewards and incentives registry for open science to support researchers in practising open science.

5.3.1.3 FAIRsFAIR

The FAIRsFAIR project ([Fostering FAIR Data Practices in Europe](#)) is working to define guidelines towards a FAIRness approach to data and service management for data repositories of all disciplines by providing a platform for using and implementing the FAIR principles in the day-to-day work of research data providers and repositories all around Europe. FAIRsFAIR will play a key role in the development of global standards for FAIR certification of repositories and the data within them contributing to those policies and practices that will turn the EOSC programme into a functioning infrastructure. FAIRsFAIR will also deliver essential FAIR dimensions of the Rules of Participation (RoP) and regulatory compliance for participation in the EOSC. The EOSC governance structure will use these FAIR-aligned RoPs to establish whether components of the infrastructure function in a FAIR manner.

RDA is a partner of the FAIRsFAIR initiative via the Research Data Alliance Foundation. In addition, different members of RDA Working and Interest Groups have been nominated as potential candidates for the two Expert Groups that the project will establish: the High Level Advisory Committee and the European Group on FAIR Champions.

5.3.2 The RDA national node network support

As briefly introduced in section 5.1.2, RDA Europe 4.0 has built a network of 22 national nodes that are proactively working to provide input and content to enrich the National Digital Agendas of the EU countries and supporting the promotion and adoption of RDA Outputs and recommendations in their countries and in the European Open Science Cloud. The national nodes are key to realising the objective of consolidating a strong European research data community that enables common European contributions to the RDA work and governance, globally. Over the course of RDA Europe 4.0, the national nodes have been pursuing and piloting options for sustainability beyond the project period. This section describes progress and plans of the individual nodes in relation to sustainability.

Nine nodes began with the project kick-off in March 2018, with an additional 13 joining the network during 2019 via three open calls. For the initial nine nodes, the deliverable D3.1 “Working plan for each National Node, with links to national structures” included strategies for sustaining node activities beyond the RDA Europe 4.0 project and were further expanded in D5.4 “Interim Sustainability Report”. For new nodes, grants from the RDA Europe project offered “seed-funding” to help establish and support a national RDA community. Ideally, the momentum provided by node activities **assists nodes to find a means of transitioning to self-financing and continued operation within the global framework of RDA Regional Engagement** (i.e. becoming a recognised RDA Region with a specific MoU or Partnership Agreement with the RDA Foundation).

In general, several strategies have emerged as elements to sustain national node activities beyond the current RDA Europe 4.0 project. Some will continue operation **via a dedicated legal entity** (e.g. Austria, Germany), some have already joined the **regional engagement programme** (e.g. France), but most will maintain the **RDA node activities via collaboration with other initiatives and as contributions to the National Digital Agenda** (e.g. Bulgaria, Denmark, Estonia, Lithuania, Netherlands, UK). In the majority of cases, the organisation or group of organisations that coordinated the node during RDA Europe 4.0 has committed to continuing its role and contributing resources for future activities (e.g. Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Norway, Sweden).

As discussed earlier, RDA’s Regional Engagement is key to the overall RDA global sustainability strategy and pathways to becoming a recognised RDA Region are under discussion within the network and individual nodes. As noted earlier, **RDA France has formally transitioned to a recognised RDA Region with the signature of regional partnership in 2019 between RDA global and the French Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation (MESRI) and the French Centre national de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS)**. Regardless of formal status, all national node official representatives will have the opportunity to participate in the RDA Regional Assembly (first meeting to be held virtually in September 2020), which is a forum open to new, aspiring and contributing regions.

The following paragraphs briefly summarise the sustainability strategy for each individual national node. Overall, the plans prioritise a strongly collaborative approach with relevant national and European research data and open science communities, seeking to build on the achievements and benefits experienced within the national context during RDA Europe 4.0. These summaries should be seen as works-in-progress as nodes are in the process of discussing and delivering fuller sustainability plans to their partner organisations and stakeholders.

RDA Austria started operation prior to being formally established as an RDA Europe node and will continue its activities as a legal entity. The legal entity RDA Austria is open to individual and institutional memberships to ensure commitment to the initiative. Although not providing significant operational funds, the participation of both individuals and institutions enables organic growth with a strategic approach, gathering further resources from institutions, industry partners, SMEs and large data centres in Austria. As well

as (minimal) membership fees, financial support will be delivered via in-kind contributions and seeking further funding sources. Node activities to be continued include networking activities and further actions depending on funding sources.

The RDA node in **Bulgaria** plans to continue activities as part of the national digital agenda. Stakeholders will include the Sofia University, the Institute of Mathematics and Informatics, the Bulgarian Open Science Cloud (open science portal), the Ministry of Education and Science, Institute of Information and Communication Technology - Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Technical University - Sofia, the National Centre for information and documentation (NACID), and software companies (Ontotex). Several funding sources are foreseen, including National Research Programs: ICT in Science, Education, and Security; Operational Program Science and Education for Smart Growth via the Centre of Excellence UNITE hosted by the University of Sofia (until 31.12.2023) and a Horizon 2020 funded project (EuroCC - to start September 2020 for 24 months). The focus of future node activities will include workshops on relevant topics (e.g. open access to data obtained within publicly funded projects, FAIR data etc.), the training of researchers (intensive courses, expansion of data science courses with new lectures) and training of industry workers (courses on demand). Currently the RDA BG node cooperates closely with the BG representative on the EOSC Governing Board and plans to continue its involvement in and contribution to EOSC.

In **Croatia**, the RDA node will continue activities with the support and coordination by SRCE - University of Zagreb, University Computing Centre, and collaboration with all stakeholders that showed interest during the project phase: Croatian Science Foundation, University Library Rijeka, University of Split Library, City and University Library in Osijek and National and University Library in Zagreb. The node is also open to new stakeholders including the Ministry of Science and Education and OpenAIRE NOAD. Croatian RDA node activities will be carried out as part of regular activities of SRCE and partner institutions as an in-kind contribution. SRCE will combine RDA activities together with the activities of development and maintenance of the national research e-infrastructure components like DABAR (national repository infrastructure) and HRČAK (national publishing platform for OA journals). Ministry support will be sought. The focus of future node activities will include workshops on relevant topics (e.g. best practices for research data management based on RDA outputs), training of researchers (intensive courses, new data science courses), continuation of cooperation with Croatian Science Foundation established during the project phase on implementation and support for DMPs. SRCE e-Infrastructure Days (SRCE DEI) conference and events organized by other partners will be used to raise the awareness of the importance of RDM. Croatian RDA node has established links with EOSC related stakeholders: EOSC GB representative of Croatia, and EOSC projects such as NI4OS-Europe (National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe) and plans to participate in the work of the future EOSC partnership on national level.

In the **Czech Republic**, the RDA node will continue with support and coordination by the Plan4all association and collaboration with all stakeholders that showed interest during the project phase. This includes the Plan4all members as well as other organisations such as funding bodies and public authorities in the Czech Republic. Strong links will be maintained with other international organisations such as the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) and Big Data Value Association (BDVA). The value of the node will be as a contact for communication within the Czech research environment, providing feedback to funding authorities from scientists and researchers, and assisting in the adoption of RDA outputs.

The **Danish** RDA node has been working in the framework of the national RDM strategy and will continue its work as part of the national digital agenda. The main stakeholders and participants will be research support staff and data stewards from Danish universities who were earlier part of the National Forum for Research Data Management. The Danish e-Infrastructure Cooperation (DeiC) is the national research infrastructure provider and strategically positioned for a national role in data management and data stewardship. DeiC is an Organisational Member of RDA, and the RDA node will continue to be anchored at DeiC. In terms of financial support, it is anticipated that DeiC will fund arrangements and secretariat

support as an in-kind contribution. Participation, travel costs and work hours for participants will be funded in-kind by participants' organisations, as has been the case in the earlier DM Forum. The activities to be continued by the node will include part of DM Forum community activities, such as knowledge sharing meetings, webinars, mailing list, etc. The node also intends to strengthen their collaboration with GO FAIR and the Data Together group (of which RDA is part).

In **Estonia**, the activities of the RDA node will become part of the national digital agenda. The University of Tartu Library will maintain RDA node activities in cooperation with the university's grant office. Node activities will be also maintained in collaboration with OpenAIRE activities. In cooperation with the Ministry of Education and Research, the aim is for node activities to form part of the Estonian Open Science strategy and the Estonian Open Science Competence Center which is being developed. Financial support will come from library funding that supports the Open Science working group and funding applications to the Ministry of Education and Research. The node will continue its links to EOSC activities, such as EOSC Nordic, EOSC FAIR WG, OpenAIRE. The aim of ongoing node work will include raising the awareness of Open Science, open research data, and helping researchers understand the usefulness of RDA and what they can gain from it.

The RDA node in **Finland** will be maintained in collaboration with other initiatives and the activities of the RDA node will become part of the national digital agenda. The Finnish node will operate as a virtual network of experts organizing national events and activities, and participating in RDA activities as a part or in addition to their other duties. CSC and the Finnish Open Science & research coordination will likely be able to offer some in-kind coordination resources. The stakeholders involved will be CSC - IT Center for Science Ltd, the Finnish EOSC Platform, the Finnish Open Science and Research Coordination, and the Finnish Committee for Research Data. As the Finnish Open Science and Research Data landscape is already quite mature and crowded, the way forward for RDA in Finland will be to embed it into existing structures and activities. RDA in Finland will maintain links to regional and European initiatives through the stakeholder organisations and individuals in the network. For example, CSC is involved in numerous initiatives beyond Finnish borders, on the Nordic, European, and Global levels alike. The Finnish Open Science & Research coordination will link RDA to OpenAIRE, CODATA, WDS, GO FAIR, LIBER, LERU, ALLEA, etc. In addition, RDA will be an important stakeholder interface and policy discussion platform for the upcoming Finnish EOSC platform. At the Finnish Open Science & Research collaboration, the RDA organization and its outputs will remain as key benchmarks. In addition, a working group focusing on international research data networks and initiatives will be formed, which will monitor RDA, CODATA, WDS, OpenAIRE, EOSC, GO FAIR, and other key players, and disseminate to the Finnish research community important work done there, and also vice versa.

In **France**, the RDA node will continue as a collaboration between stakeholders and as part of the national digital agenda. The main stakeholders are the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) as coordinators, with support from the Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation (MESRI) in the framework of the National Open Science Plan.³³ CNRS provides in-kind support and the node will have financial support from the MESRI in 2020-2021. The activities to be continued include coordination and animation of the French RDA community, interaction with the MESRI, the National Open Science Committee and the national research organisations, liaison with RDA Global and RDA Europe, dissemination of RDA activities and outputs in the national community, support to advance certification of data repositories and services, and interaction with the Research Infrastructures from the National Research Infrastructure Roadmap. In addition, the possibility to tackle additional activities in the framework of the National Open Science Plan will be assessed. The collaboration of RDA France established with the national Open Science Committee (CoSO), which is under the auspices of the MESRI, is a very positive component of the current sustainability plan. The CoSO and RDA France are establishing a common Working Group on Certification of data repositories and services.

³³ https://libereurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/SO_A4_2018_05-EN_print.pdf

In **Germany**, RDA Deutschland e.V.³⁴ is a dedicated member-driven legal entity that will take on the responsibility of dealing with RDA matters at the national level. The stakeholders involved are the German research data landscape at large (Universities, RPOs, RFOs). RDA Deutschland e.V. was formed in 2017 and operates a membership model for individuals, which will provide some financial support in addition to potential income from events. The activities sustained will include the yearly conference, sustaining the RDA Research Data Model and Vocabulary (DFT) and there are plans to establish a new journal focusing on RDM that will accept contributions in English and German. RDA Deutschland will continue its links to national regional and European initiatives, e.g. to GO FAIR and FAIR-DI. The ongoing benefits of the RDA node in Germany include raising awareness of the importance of proper RDM, realising a forum for the German RDM-Community to meet and network, organising teaching and training events on the topic of RDM, and linking up with activities in other countries.

The **Greek** RDA node will continue its activities as part of the national digital agenda, working with stakeholders participating in the National Open Science Task Force, where the RDA Greek Node is an active member. The task force consists of elected representatives from 11 academic/research organisations and 26 infrastructures, also linked to the Research and Technology-related ministry.³⁵ The task force produced a national Open Science plan proposing policies for an Open Science ecosystem in Greece. RDA-GR provided input regarding RDA viewpoints and outputs, such as CoreTrustSeal or the FAIR Data Maturity Model. In-kind contributions and collaborations (e.g. OpenAIRE Greek NOAD, HELIX) are expected to support node activities and there are ongoing discussions with the General Secretariat for Research and Technology. Node activities to be continued will include: 1) organisation of events (physical, virtual or hybrid) around Open Science and Research Data Management in cooperation with national Open Science Task Force members and/or other relevant stakeholders, including ministerial ones when relevant; and 2) activities for maintaining the Node's presence (minimum presence/best effort approach if no funding is secured). RDA Greece has established links with EOSC related members (GB/EB members of EOSC phase 1.0, EOSC projects such as NI4OS-Europe (EOSC-5b), NEANIAS (thematic area/cloud), and the OpenAIRE projects including the new legal entity, along with other fora, such as e-IRG. Most such links will persist after the RDA EU 4.0 project, especially with the projects that will continue in the next years, while new ones will be established with the new projects (EOSC-03-2020 call) and the new entities/projects that will come out of EOSC phase 2.0. In addition, there are preliminary discussions for the organisations involved in the National Open Science Task Force to take a more active role in the EOSC by forming a national Consortium which would assume the role of the Mandated Organization (MO) for Greece in EOSC. In that context, the RDA Greek Node being a member of the Task Force would contribute to EOSC, but the approach to be undertaken is still not decided. Otherwise, the RDA node will feed inputs to the other relevant EOSC entities described above, so most contributions are envisaged to be indirect.

In **Hungary**, the RDA node will continue its activities in collaboration with other initiatives and as part of the national digital agenda. The active stakeholders involved will be the national research chain, individual research institutes, the Institute for Computer Science and Control, (SZTAKI) the Library of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences, the national Open Access collaboration, and the national organisation supporting research infrastructure (KIFÜ). On a higher level the stakeholders will be the Eötvös Loránd Research Network, the Ministry for Innovation and Technology, the National Research, Development and Innovation Office, and the Hungarian Open Science Cloud. Issues of financial support are pending, although members will sustain operations offering the use of their facilities and volunteer work. The activities planned to continue include raising awareness, training and outreach, meetups, and the HRDA webportal. In addition, the node aims to conduct pilot projects, especially building FAIR repositories for various science communities. In terms of regional links, Hungary is actively involved in the NI4OS project in strong collaboration with the Hungarian academic and industrial stakeholders. Hungary is also involved in EGI activities and within EGI in EOSC related projects like EOSC-hub and EGI-ACE. The node has started a strong collaboration with the Eötvös Loránd Research Network, which will continue in order to introduce the data steward concept in every research institute of the network. Large scale

³⁴ <https://www.rda-deutschland.de/verein>

³⁵ <https://hellenicdataservice.gr/news/actions/view/412>

cloud infrastructure needed for building FAIR data repositories has been funded by the Eötvös Loránd Research Network. In future, active participation in EOSC and RDA is jointly planned by the Hungarian RDA node and the Eötvös Loránd Research Network.

The RDA node in **Ireland** will be maintained in collaboration with other initiatives and the activities will become part of the national open research agenda. The main stakeholders involved will be the National Library of Ireland (NLI) and the Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI). Financially, the node will be supported by in-kind contributions for engagement and outreach. For specific activities, it will consider applications for targeted funding via the node coordinator, NLI, or supporting organisation, the DRI. Both organisations are part of RDA's Organisational Assembly and will continue their commitment to the promotion of RDA's mission in Ireland. The activities continued under RDA Ireland will include the promotion of RDA activities and outputs and the engagement of Irish researchers and data communities with the RDA. Both NLI and DRI have promoted the involvement of RDA in the National Open Research Forum (NORF), particularly in the National Research Data Principles Working Group. There will be a continued input to the NORF Steering group for Phase 2 (the creation of a National Open Research Action Plan). The DRI Director is on the NORF Steering Group, and Ireland's newly appointed National Open Research Coordinator (from 1 Sept 2020) is based at the DRI. The NORF Phase 2 working groups will also have direct representation from RDA, and future steps including Ireland's involvement in the EOSC will be addressed by this Forum.

The RDA node in **Italy** plans to continue its activities in collaboration with other initiatives. The main stakeholders involved will be the Ministry of University and Research (MUR) and the Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure (ICDI)³⁶. The node will be supported by in-kind contributions from CNR to coordinate the node, while the ICDI network through the MUR (Ministry of University and Research) will manage and include the node activity in its agenda. Some of the activities in the ICDI agenda will be provided in-kind by the institutions in the forum (ICDI is becoming a legal entity in the upcoming months) and the MUR will partially support ICDI activities. Node activities to be continued include events organisation, dissemination of RDA activity to the Italian community and vice versa, the realisation of an Italian National Competence Center for EOSC, and support for Italian members of the RDA node for the participation in the RDA plenary/meeting of the RDA WGs and IGs. In relation to EOSC, ICDI is one of the four organisations that are members of the first EOSC partnership. In addition, ICDI is designing a national EOSC Competence Center.

In **Lithuania**, the RDA node will continue in collaboration with other initiatives and as part of the national digital agenda. The main stakeholders will be representatives of research funding and research implementing institutions represented in the current node and, in addition, representatives of the Research Council of Lithuania and representatives of the research infrastructures. Financial support will be delivered via institutional funding (Kaunas University of Technology) plus project-based funding (national funding opportunities). The main focus of ongoing activities will be training and information dissemination. In addition, there is a need for a national Open Science platform that will encompass the information on the national landscape of research infrastructures, both national and international initiatives. Attempts will be made to work towards establishing such a platform. Regional and European links include EOSC Nordic and OpenAIRE. Sustainability plans have been discussed with representatives of the Ministry of Education, Science and Sport, who have expressed support for Kaunas University of Technology as a coordinator of OS – related activities in the future.

The RDA node in the **Netherlands** will continue in collaboration with other initiatives. Specifically, the Dutch RDA node will become integrated in the National Coordination Point Research Data Management (LCRDM). This is a national network of experts in the field of research data management. The LCRDM forms the link between policy and solution. Within LCRDM, experts work together to put RDM subjects on the agenda that are too big for one institute to tackle and need a national plan of action. LCRDM brings together research support services, policy makers, ICT specialists, managers of diverse research institutes and

³⁶ <https://www.icdi.it/en/>

research funding organisations. The LCRDM coordinates and facilitates the collaboration between the various RDM stakeholders. Once the national node is part of LCRDM, the activities will be supported by the overall budget of LCRDM. LCRDM is funded by the national federation of Dutch universities (VSNU) and LCRDM itself is coordinated by SURF as part of the SURF-innovation programme Open Science. Embedding RDA related activities in this structure will hopefully provide enough financial sustainability. In terms of activities, the RDA.NL community and mailing list have already been integrated into the LCRDM community and mailing list. The focus of the activities will remain on raising awareness and promoting adoption of RDA recommendations and outputs and on soliciting input from Dutch data experts into the activities of the RDA IGs and WGs.

In **Norway**, the RDA node will continue in collaboration with other initiatives and as part of the national digital agenda. The node will continue to consist of the current partners in the NO-RDA Consortium, namely Unit - The Directorate for ICT and Joint Services in Higher Education and Research, University of Oslo, University of Bergen, NTNU - Norwegian University of Science and Technology, UiT The Arctic University of Norway, Uninett Sigma2, and NSD - Norwegian Centre for research Data. The sustainability plan is yet to be finalised, but financial support will mainly be delivered via own contributions (in-kind) from the members of the NO-RDA Consortium. Some financing may be provided by UNIT - The Directorate for ICT and Joint Services in Higher Education and Research. Activities continued by the node will include networking; helping to facilitate and exchange knowledge, experience and expertise within the area of open science and research data sharing. In the area of skills development, the node aims to establish a national framework for competence requirements for research support staff. Another activity relates to preparing an authoritative Norwegian terminology related to open research and research data management. Finally, the node plans to continue communication activities and aims to front a national "Open Data Champions" program. In relation to regional links, there are ongoing discussions with UNIT on the aspect of including NO-RDA as an active part of a national project that aims to coordinate efforts to create a common platform for the administration of (national, public) research data. There are currently no direct links to European initiatives, but several of the partner institutions are involved in projects like SSHOC (Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud) and EOSC / EOSC Nordic.

In **Portugal**, the activities of the RDA node will become part of the national digital agenda. In terms of stakeholders, the node currently operates on the basis of 3 groups: the Board, Advisory board, and RDA members in Portugal. Important institutional stakeholders are the universities/institutions in the board, the infrastructures from the national roadmap and the Portuguese science funding agency, FCT. It is possible to further explore this model and expand the organisations involved and the number of members; some support is required from the funding agency/ the institutions on the board. Financial support is an ongoing discussion, but potential sources are the Portuguese science funding agency, in-kind contributions from institutions in the RDA-pt Board, and infrastructures of the national roadmap. The activities to be continued include participating in RDA IG/WG and plenaries; the identification of opportunities for the adoption of recommendations by organisations and research groups and the sponsorship of the corresponding adoption stories; introduction of sessions on RDM-related topics in disciplinary events. In addition, the node has the potential to evolve to a more operational structure, one that can fill an important gap identified in recent analyses: the match between needs and requirements on the side of researchers and practitioners and the solutions and recommendations that are available in the community. Regarding broader links, collaboration between the RDA-pt Board and the national EOSC representatives is already in place, with joint meetings, cross-consultation and the co-organisation of events. RDA-pt Board members are currently contributing to the definition of the national "Open Data Strategy" (EDA). The experience of the RDA node and the community it has gathered are essential to the implementation of the strategy, with action that are expected to start in early 2021.

The RDA node in **Romania** will be sustained as a collaborative activity coordinated by the OS Hub Romania part of UEFISCDI, with the support of the Ministry of Education and Research. The open science activities carried by UEFISCDI will reach all relevant stakeholders and research communities in the country. UEFISCDI has the capacity to self-sustain activities implied by the role of being an RDA Node and secure self-

funding for activities related to the promotion of open research data and data driven innovation (beyond September 2020) through the projects and activities carried by the Open Science Hub. Future activities will include those related to dissemination (maintaining a platform of dialogue at national level to manage information and exchange needs of the scientific community, policy and decision-makers and the general public); providing input to the process of developing and updating the national strategic framework for open science; activities and projects in the field of open science and data-driven innovation at national level; and ensuring an open constant dialogue and alignment to the European policies and RDA initiatives, along with OpenAIRE, EOSC involvements and collaborations. Regional and European links held by UEFISCDI include participation in OpenAIRE (as OpenAIRE legal entity members), intention to be part of the EOSC Association under development, participation in NI4OS Europe, and membership of Science Europe. As the RDA node in Romania, it continues its mission of: a) offering national support for the open research data initiatives and for the overall transition to OS, as well as b) being the main connector to the international community with regards to open access and open research data in order to align the national developments to the European OS strategy.

The **Slovenian** node plans to continue its activities as a collaboration with other initiatives and as part of the national science development strategy. The Slovenian RDA node will cooperate with all stakeholders gathered in the Slovenian Open Science Community and consult with policy makers and research funding organisations in order to respond to their needs. Financing of the node will be determined within the action plan of the future national open science strategic policy, with the goal to sustain RDM related activities in Slovenia. Details are expected to be determined in the National research law and related strategic research development documents to be ready at the beginning of 2021. The node will continue its ad hoc working groups as established during RDA Europe 4.0 on selected harmonised data services' functionalities (minimal standards, certification, evaluation, crediting); RDM institutional and disciplinary tools and training; and involvement of journals and learned societies. General coordination and communication, events organisation, participation in global RDA, proposals for projects of RDA implementations and building consortia for national projects addressing priorities in the strategy is also foreseen. The national Node will be a key stakeholder of the future Slovenian Open Science Community established as a part of the European Open Science Initiative as planned in the regional NI4OS project. In the future Slovenian Open Science Community, of which the RDA node will be one of the constitutive members, connection will be established to the national open science cloud institutional framework and as such integrated with the European Open Science Cloud. RDA node activities are closely related to almost all issues of EOSC, and managing research data (e.g. DMP, institutional and disciplinary steward support) is one of the key topics. As such, the national OSC initial concept considers the activities of the RDA node as extremely important not only at managing and long-term archiving of research data but also at building the needed data experts and researchers' support and knowledge exchange infrastructures, including end-user education.

The RDA node in **Spain** will continue beyond RDA Europe 4.0 as a collaboration between initiatives, with the main stakeholders being the Spanish national network for E-Science and the Spanish part of EOSC. Financial support is a pending issue, but will potentially be sourced from the Spanish Ministry for Science and Innovation. Depending on the level of support, the Spanish node will be able to continue its activities as usual and/or continue to carry out networking activities, to promote RDA events, plenaries and open calls with best effort. The node will maintain links that have been established with EOSC and other open science initiatives. It will continue as a national contact point of reference for questions related to RDA and open science related activities in Spain. It will operate the RDA Spain group for dissemination and Spanish members of RDA will be supported in competing for RDA future grants and to increase visibility in the global RDA activities.

In **Sweden**, the Swedish National Data Service (SND) will continue to support RDA Sweden as part of its ordinary mission, mainly by providing a platform for dissemination of information about RDA activities and outputs, and by supporting adoption of RDA recommendations. In a longer perspective, it is foreseen that RDA Sweden can become part of the national digital agenda (RDM national strategy, open science strategy). In terms of financial support, during the current financial period 2018-2022, SND will integrate RDA node activities in the core workplan for the organisation. In the project plan for 2023-

2027, to be developed throughout next year, SND intends to incorporate national RDA-related activities. Activities that will be continued by RDA Sweden will include networking and dissemination. For instance, RDA Sweden foresees a continued series of dissemination activities in the form of mini-workshops and seminars (both virtual and physical), held both standalone and co-organised with meetings and conferences held throughout Sweden. In addition, RDA Sweden will maintain regional and European links built during RDA Europe 4.0, including discussions related to cooperation between the Nordic RDA nodes. There may be some potential funding opportunities from the Council of Nordic Ministers, towards collaborations on specific topics.

UK participation in the RDA node will continue through the involvement of several UK organisations including Jisc, UKRI, the Digital Curation Centre, and the Wellcome Trust. The continuing activities will include dissemination and events (virtual/F2F), coordinated with other UK research data initiatives (for example RDMF, OpenAIRE UK NOAD). In 2021, the UK node will be supporting the hosting of RDA Plenary 17 through its collaborating partners. In terms of regional or European links, the node will continue to liaise and organise closely with initiatives such as EOSC, OpenAIRE, etc and global RDA activities. RDA will remain an important part of the UK international research data activities, alongside initiatives such as CODATA, GO FAIR and WDS, for example.

5.3.3 The in kind contributions for the continuation of RDA: the RDA Working & Interest Groups

The technical heart of RDA will remain its Working and Interest Groups supported by over 5,700 European individuals that contribute to RDA in a voluntary manner.

The FAIR-related Working Groups

Several RDA Working groups and Interest groups address the question how the FAIR principles are best embedded in the research data landscape. In doing so a number addresses or supports the aims of the EOSC FAIR Data EG and a number of the subsequent EOSC WGs. The [RDA Working Group "FAIR data maturity model"](#), established in January 2019, has developed a common set of core assessment criteria for FAIRness accompanied by a generic and expandable self-assessment model for measuring the implementation level of the FAIR data principles. This will improve the interoperability of existing and emerging assessment methodologies for FAIR, allow the combination and comparison of their results and increase the homogeneity of the FAIR metric tools developed at global level. The group's work is currently undergoing assessment as an RDA recommendation³⁷.

A relevant slide from the EC³⁸ mentioning relevant linkages between FAIR and RDA is reported in Figure 2.

³⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/fair-data-maturity-model-wg/outcomes/fair-data-maturity-model-specification-and-guidelines>

³⁸ FAIRsFAIR kick-off meeting, 14-15 March 2019.

Figure 2: FAIR and RDA (EC slide)

In addition, there are other RDA Working and Interest Groups working on FAIR matters:

- [Brokering Framework WG](#)
- [Data Versioning WG](#)
- [DMP Common Standards WG](#)
- [Exposing Data Management Plans WG](#)
- [Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership WG](#)
- [WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG](#)
- CURE-FAIR WG (Curation of FAIR data & code)
- FAIR4RS (WG) (FAIR research software)
- Raising FAIRness in health data & health research WG

FAIRsharing joint RDA/Force11 WG. The FAIRsharing joint RDA/Force11 WG output has recently been fully recommended by the RDA. The output from this WG is among the 17 RDA “flagship” Outputs (full list at <https://tinyurl.com/RDArecommendations>), which are the official endorsed results of the groups, substantiated by community adoption and use. The use and adoption of FAIRsharing has been documented in *Nature Biotechnology* (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-019-0080-8>) and further information on FAIRsharing activities and uptake is available at <https://fairsharing.org/communities>.

COVID-19 WG - Recommendations and Guidelines

As the scale of the COVID-19 pandemic became clear, RDA used accelerated processes to establish a series of groups tasked with producing guidelines which would assist data and software reuse in COVID-19 related research. The work was managed by an umbrella COVID-19 group³⁹ with significant European involvement from chair level down, and established a number of sub-groups to tackle specific aspects of the problem in Clinical settings, Community participation, Epidemiology, Legal & Ethical issues, Omics, Social sciences and Research software. The group was established in March 2020, rapidly drew over 300 members, and produced its final outputs in June 2020, with . This is a clear demonstration of the ability of RDA to mobilise a broadly-based set of skills from a diverse community to produce rapid answers to urgent challenges when necessary.

The GEDE Group

The [Group of European Data Experts in RDA \(GEDE-RDA\)](#), which includes delegates from 50 European research infrastructures, will continue working to promote, foster and drive the discussions and consensus forming on creating guidelines, core components and concrete data fabric configuration building based on a bottom-up process.

6 Conclusions

The **European Council Conclusions on Shaping Europe's Digital Future**⁴⁰, approved on 9 June 2020, states that “*open science principles and Research Data Alliance recommendations are useful for supporting the decision-making authorities in promoting a flexible common approach for the collection, processing and availability of data*” and welcomes this in the context of the development of EOSC. This is a very significant occurrence and a very important recognition from one of the highest European Union bodies of the work of RDA.

The current RDA Europe 4.0 partners and national nodes, together with the European Commission (INFRAEOSC-03 call) recognise the value of RDA’s global forum and European activities and are committed to sustaining them. The strengths of RDA in the European context include the global reach of RDA, its ‘neutral’ position and platform, its role in forming continental (European) cohesion on matters related to research data, its penetration in national communities through membership at the individual and organisational levels as well via the national nodes, and RDA’s role in the broader vision and

³⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-covid19>

⁴⁰ <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-8711-2020-INIT/en/pdf>

roadmap for Open Science in Europe, linked to developments within the European Open Science Cloud.

As discussed in Section 3 on ‘Strategic Foundations’, a number of vehicles are possible to operate and finance the future activities of RDA in Europe, and work has been done in the context of the RDA Europe 4.0 project to identify and appraise options, both at the European and national node level. The evaluation and piloting of sustainability paths has required close alignment with developments at the global RDA level, including endorsement of any proposed organisational structure by the RDA Foundation and Council.

The present document summarises the RDA Europe sustainability path from 2021 onwards

- A. *The RDA Belgium Foundation*
- B. *The funding streams under the European Framework Programmes (H2020 and Horizon Europe): INFRAEOSC-03 - EOSC Future proposal; EOSC Secretariat open call; FAIRsFAIR*
- C. *The RDA national node network support and the regional engagement programme*
- D. *The in-kind contributions for the continuation of RDA: the RDA Working & Interest Groups*

7 References

- /1./ Grant Agreement “RDA Europe 4.0” (number 777388), amendment of April 2019
- /2./ Fotis Karayannis et al.: “RDA Europe Task Force on Sustainability – Final Report”, RDA Europe 3 – 28 February 2018.